

MONTEVITIS

Together for the mitigation of climate change's impact on viticulture

Book of Abstracts

Seminar Perspectives for Climate-Smart Viticulture in Europe

Vila Real, Portugal

December 12th 2024

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
FIRENZE

LUXEMBOURG
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY

LIST

spi
Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação

BUK

VINARIJA
VUCINIC

Book of Abstracts

Seminar Perspectives for Climate-Smart Viticulture in Europe

12th December 2024

University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro
Quinta de Prados
5000-801 Vila Real
Portugal

Organizing Committee:

Coordinators:

António Carlos Pinheiro Fernandes

João Carlos Andrade Santos

Collaborators:

André Filipe Monteiro Claro

André Ribeiro da Fonseca

Helder Fraga

José Manuel Duarte da Cruz

Nazaret Crespo Cotrina

Teresa Raquel Macedo de Freitas

All abstracts presented at Seminar Perspectives for Climate-Smart Viticulture in Europe are registered under the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14355441>.

The content of each abstract is the sole exclusive responsibility of the authors.

This research was funded by the MONTEVITIS project “Integrating a comprehensive European approach for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Montenegro viticulture”, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe—the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021–2027)—under grant agreement n° 101059461 (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101059461>).

Thematic Seminar: Perspectives for Climate-Smart Viticulture in Europe

Day 3: 12th December 2024

Venue: UTAD – Quinta de Prados, 5000-801 Vila Real

[Escola de Ciências da Vida e do Ambiente - Edifício das Geociências](#)

Thematic Seminar: Perspectives for Climate-Smart Viticulture in Europe

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| 9:00 - 9:10 | Opening Session |
| 9:10 - 9:25 | VineAdapt2Climate project results (Pag. 4)
André Fonseca (UTAD) |
| 9:25 - 9:40 | Aridity during Grapevine Growth Stages in Extremadura (Southwest Spain) (Pag. 5)
Abelardo Garcia (UEX) |
| 9:40 - 9:55 | Impact of Climate Change on Viticulture in Extremadura: Future Scenarios and Differential Vineyard Management (Pag. 6)
Francisco J. Moral (UEX) |
| 9:55 - 10:10 | Optimizing the vegetative-productive vine balance through UAV-Based image analysis (Pag. 7)
Riccardo Rossi (UNIFI) |
| 10:10 - 10:40 | Smart Viticulture (Pag. 8 and 9)
Raul Morais & Joaquim Sousa (UTAD) |
| 10:40 - 11:10 | Coffee break |
| 11:10 - 12:10 | Discussion session on future collaboration
All partners |
| 12:10 - 12:30 | Closing ceremony |

VineAdapt2Climate project results

André Fonseca¹

¹Institute for Innovation, Capacity Building and Sustainability of Agri-Food Production (Inov4Agro), Centre for the Research and Technology of Agro-Environmental and Biological Sciences (CITAB), University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, 5001-801 Vila Real, Portugal

Abstract

Understanding the spatial variability of microclimates is essential for sustainable and optimized grape production in vineyard plots. This research employed a novel approach by integrating the NicheMapR microclimate model and the STICS crop model, with multiple climate data sources to analyze two vineyard plots: Quinta do Bomfim in northern Portugal and Herdade do Esporão in southern Portugal. The methodology enabled the development of microclimatic analyses at an unprecedented 10-meter spatial resolution for various climate variables. Hourly data from local weather stations were combined with ERA5-land hourly data, which underwent quantile mapping bias correction. These corrected data were then used to bias correct EURO-CORDEX model simulations. The research allowed to calculate climate extremes and bioclimatic indices specifically for viticulture at very high resolution, providing insights into grape phenology at each site for historical (1981–2010) and future periods (2041–2070, 2071–2100) under two Representative Concentration Pathway scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). At the 10-meter scale, variations in temperature, precipitation, and other climate indices were mapped to identify potential spatial shifts within each vineyard plot. Results showed that microclimate variations were more pronounced in areas with complex topography, whereas smoother slopes exhibited negligible variability. Shifts in key phenological stages, such as flowering, fruit filling, maximal leaf area index, physiological maturity, and harvest, along with yield changes, were also analysed. Results revealed earlier phenological stages, shortened growth periods, and significant yield declines. This research offers a robust framework for microclimate analysis in vineyards. By integrating geospatial data, ERA5-land data, the microclimate NicheMapR model and the STICS crop model, the research advances the understanding of both current and projected microclimates, providing valuable tools for viticulturists to adapt to future climate scenarios.

Aridity during Grapevine Growth Stages in Extremadura (Southwest Spain)

Abelardo García-Martín^{1, *}, and Luis L. Paniagua¹

¹Department of Agricultural and Forestry Engineering. School of Agricultural Engineering, University of Extremadura (UEX), Avda. Adolfo Suárez s/n 06007 Badajoz, Spain; abgarcia@unex.es (A.G.-M)*; lpsimon@unex.es (L.L.P.)

Abstract

Aridity is a significant factor influencing global agriculture, due to rising temperatures, rainfall variability, and the increasing frequency and intensity of droughts, among other factors. The De Martonne aridity index is a valuable tool for assessing spatial and temporal variations in aridity in agricultural regions. It can be employed to characterise the climate of agricultural regions and to evaluate their vulnerability to climate change.

This study examines the impact of aridity on viticulture in Extremadura, utilizing the De Martonne aridity index (IDM) to assess spatial and temporal variations in climate across different grapevine growth stages. The study analyzes data from 108 weather stations over 32 years (1989–2020) to determine mean aridity conditions and identify vulnerable areas within the Ribera del Guadiana Protected Designation of Origin (PDO).

The findings indicate that Extremadura's climate is predominantly Mediterranean, with significant variations in aridity throughout the grapevine growth cycle. The dormancy stage is characterized as extremely humid, while the berry development and ripening stages are classified as arid. This variability necessitates tailored crop management strategies to address the specific climatic conditions experienced in different sub-areas of the PDO.

The research highlights the vulnerability of grapevines to climate change, emphasizing the importance of understanding aridity patterns to inform agricultural practices. The study also underscores the need for irrigation strategies to mitigate the effects of decreasing precipitation and rising temperatures, which threaten grape quality and production sustainability.

In conclusion, this spatial analysis provides valuable insights into how aridity influences grapevine growth and offers a framework for developing adaptive agricultural policies aimed at enhancing resilience in viticulture under changing climatic conditions. The results contribute to the broader understanding of the interactions between climate and agriculture in Mediterranean regions, emphasizing the importance of localized studies in addressing the challenges posed by climate change on agricultural systems.

Impact of Climate Change on Viticulture in Extremadura: Future Scenarios and Differential Vineyard Management

Francisco J. Moral ^{1, *}, and Francisco J. Rebollo ²

¹ Department of Graphic Expression, School of Industrial Engineering, University of Extremadura (UEX), Avda. de Elvas, s/n., 06006 Badajoz, Spain; fjmoral@unex.es*

² Department of Graphic Expression, School of Agricultural Engineering, University of Extremadura (UEX), Avda. Adolfo Suárez, s/n., 06007 Badajoz, Spain; frebollo@unex.es

Abstract

It is known how weather condition is the main factor affecting winegrape production. Consequently, it is important the analysis of the expected consequences of climate change on vineyards. In Extremadura (southwestern Spain), most of the region will be too hot for viticulture around 2040 according to a possible future scenario after conducting different projections.

Moreover, modern oenology prioritises the production of high-quality wines, with the quality potential beginning in the vineyard, where grape and eventual wine quality are influenced by soil properties. As essential soil characteristics, such as texture, organic matter content, and cation exchange capacity, vary across the vineyard, uniform vineyard management may not be optimal for enhancing grape quality. Identifying zones with similar soil features to apply targeted management is therefore essential. A case study was carried out in a 3.3-hectare vineyard near Évora, Portugal, using a DUALEM 1S non-contact sensor to measure soil apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) and producing a kriged ECa map. Both ECa and elevation maps facilitated the identification of homogeneous zones, or management zones (MZs), through clustering. These MZs were validated by analysing soil properties (texture, pH, organic matter, phosphorous, potassium, exchange bases and cation exchange capacity) from 20 soil samples across the MZs. Additionally, validation through Rasch measures was based on a probabilistic model that integrated soil property data from each sample point, enabling clearer MZ comparisons by simplifying each zone to a single representative value. Finally, a vegetation index provided further validation by assessing plant responses in each MZ. Site-specific management in viticulture is the most efficient way to improve decision-making through the consideration of the soil spatial patterns, particularly in the expected future scenarios with warmer conditions.

Optimizing The Vegetative-Productive Vine Balance Through UAV-Based Image Analysis

Riccardo Rossi¹

¹ Department of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Forestry (DAGRI). Piazzale delle Cascine, 18.50144 Florence, Italy; r.rossi@unifi.it

Abstract

The viticulture sector faces the dual challenge of maintaining high-quality production levels under the pressure of climate change while simultaneously reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Addressing this trade-off calls the adoption of sustainable approaches within the framework of climate-smart viticulture (CSV). These practices are designed to enhance the resilience of vineyards to climate change, minimize the emissions and promote sustainable wine production. A cornerstone of CSV is the use of advanced monitoring technologies, such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), which offer crucial insights into plant status, enabling farmers to make informed decisions that optimize both vineyard productivity and environmental sustainability.

In this context, we developed an automated pipeline to process three-dimensional (3D) models of vineyards generated from UAV imagery and extract morphological features at the single-plant level, including canopy height (cm), area (cm²), and volume (cm³). Metrics extracted from 3D-models of a Tuscan vineyard (San Felice, Siena, Italy) at the flowering, fruit-setting, and maturity stages were used as proxies for key vegetative-productive balance indices: the Ravaz index, Growth-Yield Balance (GYB) index, and Renewed Dry Matter (RDM) index, which were collected through destructive surveys measuring fresh and dry fruits (FW) and pruning weight (PW) within ten 10x10 meters plots. The canopy area extracted at fruit-setting enabled the accurate estimation of PW ($R^2 = 0.76^{***}$), Ravaz index ($R^2 = 0.61^{**}$), and GYB ($R^2 = 0.65^{**}$) over the monitored vines, allowing the creation of vegetative-productive balance maps for the entire vineyard. These preliminary results suggest that the proposed approach can effectively guide harvest planning, optimize pruning, and improve canopy management throughout the season, addressing productivity imbalances while minimizing interventions and emissions. This methodology aligns with the principles of CSV, promoting more sustainable and efficient vineyard management in the face of climate change.

IoT-Based Proximity Monitoring and AI-driven Insights for Precision Viticulture

Raul Morais ^{1,2,3}

¹ Department of Engineering, School of Sciences and Technology, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal; rmorais@utad.pt

² Centre for the Research and Technology of Agro-Environmental and Biological Sciences, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal

³ Institute for Innovation, Capacity Building and Sustainability of Agri-Food Production, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal

Abstract

In the era of digital agriculture, data acquisition technologies have reached a maturity level that shifts the research focus toward extracting actionable insights for smarter and more sustainable practices. This presentation explores how IoT-based proximity monitoring systems and advanced artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms are revolutionizing vineyard management. Leveraging edge computing and low-cost IoT devices, these systems provide real-time data on soil moisture, microclimate conditions, and plant phenology. Through AI, such data is transformed into actionable knowledge, supporting the early detection of anomalies, stress factors, and pest outbreaks. The presentation highlights practical applications, including predictive irrigation management, phenological stage identification, and optimized interventions for pest control using models trained on vineyard-specific data. This approach integrates heterogeneous datasets into comprehensive decision-support tools, bridging the gap between monitoring and action. By incorporating AI to model vineyard dynamics, simulate climate scenarios, and enhance resilience, this work aligns with sustainability goals, contributing to a smarter and greener future for viticulture.

UAV-Based Multispectral, Hyperspectral, and Thermal Imaging for Advanced Smart Viticulture and Vineyard Management

Joaquim J. Sousa^{1,2}

¹ Engineering Department, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD), 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal.

² Centre for Robotics in Industry and Intelligent Systems (CRIIS), INESC-TEC, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal; [jjsousa@utad.pt](mailto:jj Sousa@utad.pt)

Abstract

Technological advancements are revolutionizing agriculture, and viticulture is no exception. This presentation delves into how multispectral, hyperspectral, and thermal data obtained via Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are transforming vineyard management, offering an innovative and scientific approach to smart viticulture.

UAVs equipped with advanced sensors enable the collection of high-resolution data spanning from visible to infrared spectrums, capturing precise insights into plant health, soil variability, water stress, and even diseases such as mildew. This level of detail is achieved through the integration of multispectral and hyperspectral technologies, which provide in-depth vineyard analysis, complemented by thermal sensors that monitor leaf temperature and irrigation efficiency.

The presentation highlights practical use cases, such as grape variety classification, automatic anomaly detection, and temporal analysis of individual vine parameters. It also explores advances in data processing for hyperspectral mosaics and the application of artificial intelligence to predict and mitigate climatic and biological impacts.

This work underscores the central role of science and innovation in transitioning to a more precise, sustainable, and climate-resilient viticulture. By integrating detailed data into an efficient operational system, the proposed approach marks a milestone for digital agriculture, enabling producers to optimize practices and achieve unprecedented levels of quality and productivity.

The presentation not only informs but inspires, paving the way for the future of viticulture and unlocking the potential of UAV technology in precision agriculture.

MONTEVITIS

Together for the mitigation of climate change's impact on viticulture